

S1. Strong TSS-associated IgG artifact

Figure S1: Tornado plots and profiles of average (n=2) CPM normalized read density from CUT&RUN using IgG control antibody in normal uninjured kidney (left) and IRI (right).

S2. Signal density is positively associated with expression

S2: Left, schematic depicting raw signal based scoring calculation for IgG and H3K4me3. Right, min-max scaled signals on X axis vs RNAseq expression levels on Y axis comparing IgG signal, H3K4me3 signal, and H3K4me3 score. R represents Spearman's R between CUT&RUN per-gene scores and RNAseq expression. To the right, histograms visualize the unnormalized distribution of scores and signals across all genes.

S3: Top GO terms, semantic clustering of GO results, and overlaps with bivalent genes

A. Bivalent genes in normal kidney

B. Epigenetically activated bivalent genes

C. Activated bivalent genes

D. Bivalent genes IRI

S3: Top GO terms (Left), Semantically clustered GO terms (Center), and overlap with bivalent ES cell datasets (Right) for bivalent gene calls in normal kidney (A), epigenetically activated bivalent gene calls (B), epigenetically and transcriptionally activated bivalent gene calls (C), and bivalent gene calls in IRI (D). p-values for significance of overlap between gene calls and ES bivalent datasets are calculated using Fisher's exact test.

S5. Comparison to outside datasets

A/B: Density plot showing expression in uninjured kidney versus log fold change in expression between normal and acute kidney injury from human pseudo-bulk snRNA-seq data previously reported in Lake et al. 2022. **A:** Points represent the median pseudo-bulk expression and log fold change for activated bivalent genes from each cell type. **B:** points represent expression and logFC of activated bivalent genes in proximal tubule cells. **C:** Bar chart of median log fold change for activated bivalent genes across cell types using human snRNA-seq data from Lake 2022, comparing normal and acute kidney injury. Significance assigned by Wilcoxon test for medians being greater than zero. Error bars represent standard error of the mean. **D:** log fold change in expression of Spi1 across cell types in human (left) and mouse (right) snRNA-seq data. Significance is presented as raw one-sided p-values for logFC>0 calculated from limma moderated t-statistics. Cell type abbreviations are as follows: **CD:** Collecting Duct, **CNT:** Connecting Tubule, **DCT:** Distal Convoluted Tubule, **DTL:** Descending Thin Limb, **EC:** Endothelial Cells, **FIB:** Fibroblasts, **IC:** Intercalated Cells, **IMM:** Immune, **LOH:** Loop of Henle, **PC:** Principal Cells, **PEC:** Parietal Epithelial Cells, **PT:** Proximal Tubule, **TAL:** Thick Ascending Limb